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“Personality is both a worldview, and individual characteristics of talent, and charisma, and responsiveness, and school. Permanent school of life. Professional skill is adjacent to this.”

S. Gerasimov

Professor D.P.Chukhriyenko

These words of the famous film director S. Gerasimov are fully related to the personality of Professor D.P. Chukhriyenko - Honored Scientist of the Ukrainian SSR, Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Member of the International Association of Surgeons, Board Member of the Ukrainian and Chairman of the Dnipropetrovsk Scientific Society of Surgeons, who left a noticeable trace not only in the memory of his contemporaries and subsequent generations of surgeons, but also stood at the origins of the Ukrainian anesthesiology, made a great contribution to the formation and development of our specialty in the Dnipropetrovsk region:

- he is the first of surgeons to actively use modern endotracheal anesthesia during surgical interventions in the clinic he took lead;

- under his leadership the training of anesthesiologists for practical health care of the city and region started;

- organized research on the impact of modern types of anesthesia on the patient's body in order to find the most optimal ones depending on the nature of the surgical intervention;

- carried out the training of scientific and pedagogical personnel;

- initiated the creation of a scientific community of anesthesiologists for the exchange of information, experience, improvement of knowledge.

It is important to note that in the late 50s - early 60s of the twentieth century these were only the first steps, which served as the beginning of development of anesthesiology in the city and region as an independent science and discipline.

The introduction of endotracheal anesthesia has contributed to the unprecedented expansion of the possibilities of surgery. And Dmitry Pavlovich Chukhriyenko, as an active surgeon seeking to perform thoracic operations (on the lungs and heart), understood the significance of modern anesthesiology for the further progress of not only major surgery, but other areas of practical medicine.

When M.M. Grinyov performed the first in the city and region endotracheal anesthesia in Pridneprovsk Road Hospital in 1956, Dmitry Pavlovich invited him to the post of assistant at the Department of Hospital Surgery N 2 of the Dnepropetrovsk Medical Institute, which was headed by him, having managed to see the great future of this emerging specialty.

Over the period from 1956 to 1958 in the clinic of hospital surgery N 2, more than 700 surgical interventions were performed using muscle relaxants under conditions of endotracheal anesthesia.

The wider use of endotracheal anesthesia in the medical institutions of the city and region required the training of relevant medical personnel. On the basis of the surgical department of the Dnieper Road Clinical Hospital, where the clinic of hospital surgery N 2 was located, the training of anesthesiologists began. In 1960, I also did course here.

Operates professor D.P.Chukhriyenko

In days of old, when anesthesiology made only the first steps and there were no relevant textbooks, manuals, special literature on this subject, scientific research was widely developed under the guidance of D.P. Chukhriyenko. A large pleiad of young enthusiastic staff members began to study the effects of anesthetics of those times and muscle relaxants on the organism in an experiment both in the clinic and on THEMSELVES.

Few researchers resolved to get answers to the questions by conducting experiments on themselves. M.M. Grinyov, a student of the Department of Advanced Medical Studies of the Military Medical Academy was fully captivated by the idea of using muscle relaxants as a component of general anesthesia during surgical procedures. He was deeply interested in the effect of large doses of ditilin on pain sensitivity and the functioning of the main systems of the body.

The experiment was conducted on himself and five volunteer-employees. These studies were subsequently summarized and in 1959 he defended Ph.D. thesis on the topic "Muscle relaxants with modern methods of anesthesia (clinical and experimental research)" and demonstrated in the form of the filmed movie "Experiment on Myself" at the 9th Congress of Surgeons of Ukraine, which took place in Dnipropetrovsk in 1959.

In 1965 under the guidance of Professor D.P. Chukhriyenko, M.M. Grinyov defended his doctoral thesis on the topic "The Effect of Artificial Ventilation of the Lungs, Different Types of Anesthesia and Operating Injury on the Dynamic Balance of the Internal Environment of the Body"

At the Department of Hospital Surgery N 2 the preparation of scientific and pedagogical personnel and studies for Ph.D. began. The first admission for postgraduate course in anesthesiology at our Dnipropetrovsk Medical Institute was announced at this department. And the first graduate student T.D. Tregubova under the guidance of professor D.P. Chukhriyenko successfully completed and defended her thesis on the topic "Ganglioblockers in modern anesthesia (clinical experimental study)" as early as 1961.

One after another a whole series of PhD and doctoral theses followed:

- Belyi I.S. – "Neuroplegia in various surgical interventions";
- Chebykina N.V. – "Surface endotracheal anesthesia in the surgical treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis (clinical and experimental study)";
- Dobrovolsky I.V. – "Anesthesia during lung surgery";

- Banduristy N.V. – "Anesthesia in surgical interventions on the heart";

- Filippov Yu.A. – "The effect of novocaine blockades on the absorption of toxic substances from the tissues in terms of burn shock" (PhD thesis); "Syndrome of long-term crushing of soft tissues of extremities in underground conditions" (doctoral dissertation) and others.

A powerful stream of trained highly qualified scientific and pedagogical personnel made it possible to teach anesthesiology to students and after the introduction in 1967 of senior lecture course in anesthesiology at the Department of General Surgery, led by a talented student of Professor D.P. Chukhriyenko – Professor L.N. Kovalenko, and with the creation in 1973 of an independent department – to the doctors.

As chairman of the Dnipropetrovsk Regional Scientific Society of Surgeons, D.P. Chukhriyenko deeply understood the importance of the professional community. On his initiative in 1963 a section of anesthesiologists was organized in the surgical society. In 1965 when the membership of anesthesiologists increased to 30, it became an independent regional scientific society. D.P. Chukhriyenko was its first chairman until 1966.

Society meetings were held on a monthly basis, topical issues of the specialty were discussed, lectures were given, clinical reviews were held, fellow-anesthesiologists from other cities of Ukraine and other republics were invited to share experiences and gain new knowledge.

Later D.P. Chukhriyenko acted as an opponent of dissertation papers on anesthesiology. He was an opponent of my two dissertations – PhD and doctoral.

Professor D.P. Chukhriyenko actively participated in congresses and conferences on anesthesiology held in our city, showing an abiding interest in our specialty, he always supported his students.

Years have passed. To date, a lot of new knowledge and technology has been accumulated. Our specialty stepped from the Esmarch's mask to modern, high-tech types of anesthesia and intensive care. Within the sphere of our single specialty, sub-specialties emerged (pediatric anesthesiology, cardio-, neuroanesthesiology and intensive care, hyperbaric therapy, extracorporeal detoxification, perfusionology, etc.) as a sequential stage in the development of practical and theoretical anesthesiology, which in cooperation with surgeons and other specialists contributed to the improvement of the quality of treatment of various categories of patients in terms of multi-specialty and specialized medical institutions.

Professor D.P. Chukhriyenko among the delegates of the IV Congress of Anaesthesiology of Ukraine with the Chairman of the Ukrainian Scientific Society of Anesthesiology, Professor. A.I.Treshchinsky (Dnepropetrovsk, 1984)

Today, more than 600 anaesthesiologists work in the region, dozens of anaesthesiology and intensive care units are at work, three specialized departments are in the academy, Dnipropetrovsk scientific school of anaesthesiologists has been established, incorporating 12 doctors and 115 candidates of medical sciences. In 2018 the regional center of the European School of Anaesthesiology (CEEAA) was opened under the aegis of the European Society of Anaesthesiologists (ESA).

In this progressive movement there is also the merit of Professor D.P. Chukhriyenko, who remains an indelible example of a scientist, doctor, teacher, advisor, statesman who brought up a whole pleiad of doctors, scientists known not only in Ukraine, but

also abroad. D.P. Chukhriyenko trained 18 doctors and 85 candidates of medical sciences, including anaesthesiologists.

Relay race continues. His disciples and followers are infected with his ideas, they rely on the foundation which he has created, this gives strength to creative activity in the present and inspires to the future.

At the end of my bright memories of Professor D.P. Chukhriyenko, I want to quote the words of the great thinker and scientist N. Roerich, which Dmitry Pavlovich would tell us today:

“The past is only a window to the future. Love the past, but live in the future. Fold the steps of the future from the wonderful stones of the past.”

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